

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

Deliverable n°:	D2.2
Deliverable name:	Dissemination plan
Version:	1.0
Release date:	19/06/2017
Dissemination level:	Submitted (Draft, Peer-reviewed, Submitted, Approved)
Status:	Public
Author:	PoI Olivella and Pau Lloret – UPC, Mette Magnussen, Mari Buckholm, Ketil Thomsen, Heidi Tuiskula and Håkon Duus - SmartIN

Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
0.1	09/03/2017	First draft version	Pol Olivella
0.2	09/05/2017	Second draft version	Pol Olivella
0.3	19/05/2017	Third draft version	Heidi Tuiskula
0.4	23/05/2017	Fourth draft version	Mette Magnusen
0.5	08/06/2017	Contents check	Pol Olivella
1.0	19/06/2017	Peer-reviewed	Pol Olivella

Peer reviewed by:

Partner	Reviewer
Lyse	Sindre Tøsse
SmartIN	Bernt A. Bremdal

Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
All partners and WP

Table of contents

Executive summary	6
1 Introduction	7
1.1 Dissemination objectives	7
1.2 Communication objectives	8
1.3 Partners in charge	9
2 Communication and dissemination actions	14
2.1 C&D instruments	14
2.2 Communication and dissemination obligations	17
2.3 Project workshops	17
2.4 Events planning	19
3 Communication and dissemination guidelines.....	20
3.1 Communication timetable and content plan	20
3.2 Journal and congress publications guidelines	24
3.3 Social media guidelines	25
3.4 Newsletters guidelines	26
3.5 Press releases guidelines	26
3.5.1 Frequency, purpose and target audience	27
3.5.2 Structure and content	27
3.5.3 Distribution and promotion	27
3.6 C&D activities repository	28
4 EC events.....	29
5 Technical Advisory Group.....	30
5.1 TAG definition	30
5.2 TAG objectives	30

6	Large scale events	32
	6.1.1 Target audience	32
	6.1.2 Content	32
	6.1.3 Follow-up	32

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
C&D	Communication and dissemination
EC	European Commission
EUG	Exploitation Users Group
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key performance indicators
WP	Work Package
WS	Workshop

Executive summary

The present Dissemination Plan (Deliverable 2.2) of INVADE project contains all information necessary to fulfil all communication and dissemination (C&D) objectives.

The document describes the C&D actions, defines responsible partners and collaborators, provides guidelines about journal and congress publications, newsletters and press releases. Additionally, it provides an introduction about the activities repository that will help partners to fulfil the repository correctly.

Section 4 is focused on the European Commission events and meetings to attend, section 5 explains the technical advisory group and section 6 expose the general characteristics of the large scale project events such as the target audience and content.

1 Introduction

According to the GA, the Dissemination plan must show, in detail, the activities to be performed along the life of the project; stakeholders to be addressed, related activities, activities schedule, KPIs and resources, identifying the summits and events linked to each stakeholder profile, and establishing how and when to participate. This deliverable corresponds to Task 2.1 of GA.

A short description about the difference between communication and dissemination:

To disseminate, in the field of communication, means to broadcast a message to the public without direct feedback from the audience. With dissemination, only half of this communication model theory is applied. The information is sent out and received, but no reply is given. The message carrier sends out information, not to one individual, but many in a broadcasting system. An example of this transmission of information is in fields of advertising, public announcements and speeches. Another way to look at dissemination is that of which it derives from the Latin roots, the scattering of seeds. These seeds are metaphors for voice or words: to spread voice, words, and opinion to an audience.¹

Communication is the act of conveying intended meanings from one entity or group to another through the use of mutually understood signs and semiotic rules².

For practical purposes, dissemination actions should spread information about the results obtained in the project like conclusions, recommendations and objectives accomplished as these are final results, we do not need feedback from the audience.

In contrast, communication actions should send messages about our current status, challenges faced and intentions and that requires feedback from potential stakeholders, advisory groups and audience in general.

1.1 Dissemination objectives

Dissemination objectives are:

1. Expose the flexibility system developed

¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dissemination>

² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Communication>

2. Spread the results achieved
3. Explain the barriers and difficulties found
4. Recommend good practices to deploy flexibility

1.2 Communication objectives

Communication objectives:

1. Discuss design requirements with TAG & EUG
2. Review INVADE system developed with involved stakeholders
3. Interact with end-users and collect their point of view
4. Promote the awareness of the stakeholders.
5. Harvest pertinent feedback.

1.3 Prime target groups

Deliverable 3.1 of INVADE project [1] exposes the Stakeholder plan and engagement strategies, and it complements the dissemination and communication objectives. It identifies INVADE customers, competitors, suppliers and authorities across Europe and they are C&D prime targets.

1.4 C&D Key performance indicators

In order to measure the effects of our C&D actions, the following key performance indicators (KPI) will be measured every month.

Website activity:

- Google analytics tool
- Website visits

Facebook activity:

- Followers
- Likes
- Clicks

- Range

Twitter activity:

- Followers
- Likes
- Clicks
- Range

1.5 Partners in charge

All partners are in charge of C&D actions. Explicitly, all partners and the corresponding contact persons are responsible of collaborating in:

1. Newsletters
2. Workshops
3. Demonstrations
4. Project events promotion

Table 1 Project partners and responsibilities

Partner	Responsibility
SmartIO	Webpage, flyer and video
SmartIO	Large scale event in Norway and project events promotion
SmartIO	EC events
UPC	Large scale event in Barcelona and project events promotion
UPC	Scientific publications & Project events promotion
UPC	Project poster
NTNU	Scientific publications & Project events promotion
VTT	Scientific publications & Project events promotion
eSmart	Press releases, scientific publications and programme meetings
NewEn	Press releases and programme meetings
Albena	Press releases and programme meetings
Schneider	Press releases and programme meetings
Lyse	Press releases and programme meetings
Estabanell	Press releases and programme meetings
ElaadNL	Press releases and programme meetings
GreenFlux	Press releases and programme meetings

Additionally, each partner has its specific responsibilities:

Finally, each partner has specific C&D objectives in this WP:

All partners have defined their own objectives in terms of targeted audience and instruments.

1. SmartIO:

- a. As project coordinator SmartIO will communicate all material related to the project, both objectives and outcomes, in all events which we participate (meetings, conferences, events, workshops, etc).
- b. As partner of the project SmartIO will manage communication and dissemination activities in order to empower results. Consequently, this will be executed during the project following the Work Package leader coordination and guidelines.
- c. As specified in the grant agreement SmartIO will attend all the events organized by the commission for the coordination between the different founded projects in order to improve the coordination and to optimize the different outcomes of the projects increasing the overall impact.

2. UPC:

- a. To disseminate the technology developed related with flexibility algorithms, smart grid architectures, laboratory facility capabilities and electric vehicles.
- b. To prepare the locale stakeholders situated at or close to the test sites and conditions the parties being affected for the purpose at hand.
- c. To highlight new scientific results and outstanding issues and to show how historic research has been applied and conveys this to the international research community to trigger continued scientific efforts

3. NTNU:

- a. To disseminate new knowledge on flexibility services from EVs and energy storages, as well as the the new methods for operation, sizing and placement of energy storage that are developed and applied in the project
- b. To highlight the use of the developed methods on selected Pilots and show how the applicability on other realistic case studies.

- c. To disseminate new scientific results to the public, the university students and Norwegian distribution grid companies.
4. VTT:
- a. To disseminate the technology and methods developed related with energy storages and their dimensioning, state estimation, optimal and cost-effective use, and life cycle management.
 - b. To highlight new scientific results obtained in WP6 (energy storage technologies) to the international research community.
5. eSmart:
- a. Disseminate the Flexibility cloud platform technology and functionality, including the underlying architecture and communication platform, in a general way.
 - b. In dialog with pilot owners, handle relevant issues related to pilot data management and data publication.
 - c. Promote the INVADE project and the Flexibility cloud platform to relevant stakeholders
6. NewEn:
- a. Dissemination of the applicable business models generated by the INVADE project.
 - b. The best possible dimensioning of the storage is realized for the users to increase trust and acceptance.
 - c. To promote the use of the follow-up concepts to show the marketability, under consideration of the German legal framework.
7. Albená:
- a. To disseminate the pilot structure and its goals – more renewable energy for the tourists
 - b. To show our commitment to the prevention of climate change by supporting the world energy transition
 - c. To disseminate the ease of use of renewables
 - d. To make popular our business model

- e. To create impact on local, state and European level in order to improve regulation for larger share of renewables.

8. Schneider:

- a. As WP10 leader, disseminate the project and Pilots in a general way. Explaining the final solutions adopted, and the implementation guidelines, including all issues related to pilot management and data publication.
- b. Promote the project with other partners in order to expose INVADE goals and solutions.

9. Lyse:

- a. To disseminate the Norwegian pilot setup and implementation as well as the specific lessons learned from this pilot in order to facilitate future exploitations at other sites.
- b. As the leader of WP9, Lyse will commit to disseminate the results of the work on novel business models and their implementations in the project.

10. Estabanell:

- a. To disseminate the setup (in terms of technicalities as well as customer engagement) that is found successful for the Estabanell validation site, encouraging easier future integration in other sites.
- b. To inform and involve local authorities in the new developments achieved by the INVADE project
- c. To promote the discussion and developments with other utilities by presenting and exploring the outcomes and business cases and the effects they can have.

11. ElaadNL:

- a. To disseminate the NL pilot setup and implementation regarding smart charging and flexibility management, as well as interoperability through open standards, in order to demonstrate how this supports the future role of the DSO's and other relevant stakeholders across Europe.
- b. To share information and knowledge about the INVADE pilot, to present the outcomes and to demonstrate the applicability of protocols and this kind of projects in general to DSO's and other relevant stakeholders across Europe.

12. GreenFlux:

- a. To disseminate the NL pilot setup and implementation regarding smart charging and local energy management, as well as the specific lessons learned from this pilot in order to facilitate future exploitations at other sites.
- b. To expand the pilot setups to other locations in The Netherlands and other countries to support smart charging with a flexible amount of available energy and to generate maximum impact
- c. To present the outcomes of the INVADE pilot to relevant stakeholders and at relevant events.

2 Communication and dissemination actions

2.1 C&D instruments

According to the GA, Table 2 lists all instruments to be used in the project for C&D actions and Table 3 relates responsible partner and collaborators of each C&D action and instrument.

Table 2 C&D instruments (Table 2.1 GA)

Website	It will be a key tool to raise a common understanding of the project goals and outcomes and to create an image of the project. It will be a central point of access to project progress and available documentation. The project website will be linked to the websites of the project partners and it will embed access and content from social networks.
Social networks	Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter. Average update frequency will be daily updates for Twitter and weekly updates for LinkedIn and Facebook. A close interplay between the website and the social media accounts will be created.
Press releases	Starting from the first press release in M3, three formal announcements to the national and international press and media, announcing the project start and end, but also highlighting important achievements and availability of public outcomes.
Project video	A professionally produced one project video , highlighting the vision, challenges and expected outcomes will be prepared at M18
Flyer	A flyer presenting key insights about the project in printed form to be handed out at conferences, to colleagues and to engaged or interested stakeholders. Electronic version will also be made available.
Newsletters	Four newsletters will be generated in order to announce the project, give regular updates on project progress, develop a profile, and get buy-in. It may include interviews with key stakeholders, some quotes from end users, and insights from the large project events and workshops.
Local meetings	Direct talks with the stakeholders on their premises or any other suitable place where proper attention can be achieved.
Technical Advisory Group	This is designed to gain additional technical expertise on R&D effort and demonstrations and have a more focused strategic vision. It will include a maximum of 7 members from the most important types of stakeholders and high-level scientific researchers.
Exploitation Users Group	This is an instrument for dissemination and focused preparation of an exploitation plan followed up by deployment. It will include maximum 15 representatives from municipalities, local communities, key stakeholders and members from international organisations representing worldwide emerging markets. The group is described on p.39
Project events	Two large-scale project events will be organised to achieve a greater impact on promoting the project and attracting key stakeholders at business, policy and regulatory levels.
Workshops	At least 8 technical workshops , as interactive events of technical nature, will be held to achieve specific objectives - to discuss and get feedback from experts on related technical issues and on project demonstrations and at least 2 workshops will be organised to discuss the business models and deployment potential. Indicative list of workshops is given on p. 30

Conference presentations	At least 28 presentations will be submitted to national and international conferences in order to share project's achievements with experts in the field. The selection of conferences will be made in terms of impact potential or evidence of presence of relevant experts and stakeholders. An indicative list of international conferences is given on p. 38
Conference posters	The project poster in formats appropriate to be shown to delegates in conferences and workshops, as well as in any event organised at project or partner level.
Demonstrations	Pilot demonstrations will be used to show up progress to interested stakeholders. The purpose is to be proactive and reactive, sharing project's learning with the research, public and private business communities.
Scientific Papers, Journal articles	At least 13 scientific papers will be submitted to indexed, peer-reviewed journals related with the related disciplines, (electricity generation, storage and distribution, telecoms, transport). Copies of all publications will be accessible on the project website (open access). Indicative list of peer-reviewed journals is given on p.37
Reports and other documents	Reports and other type of documents on specific topics will be posted on the project website to enable accessibility to a wide audience.
Programme meetings	H2020 programme meetings will be used as opportunities for projects to learn from each other, discuss common issues, and get feedback on project's work.

Table 3: Responsible partner (R) and collaborators (C) in each C&D instruments

Partner	Website	Social network	Press releases	Project video	Flyer	Generic newsletters	Newsletter about pilots	Local meetings	Technical Advisory Group	Exploitation Users Group	Project events	Workshops	Conference presentations	Conference posters	Demonstrations	Journal papers	Reports and other documents	Programme meetings
SmartIO	R	R	C	R	R	C	C			R	R		C	C		R	R	R
UPC	C	C	R		C	R		R	R		R	R	R	R		R	C	C
NTNU	C	C	C		C	C		C	C		C	R	C	R		R	C	
VTT	C	C			C	C		C				R	C	R		R	C	
eSmart	C	C	C		C	C		C				R	C			C	C	C
NewEn	C	C	C				C	C					C		R		C	
Albena	C	C	C				C	C					C		R		C	
Schneider	C	C	C				R	C					C		R		C	
Lyse	C	C	C				C	C		R			C		R		C	
EPESA	C	C	C				C	C					C		R		C	
Elaad	C	C	C		C	C	C	C	C				C		R		C	
GreenFlux	C	C	C		C	C	C	C	C		C		C				C	

2.2 Communication and dissemination obligations

Table 4 summarizes the project commitments from the GA

Table 4: C&D obligations

Website	1 INVADE project website: www.invadeh2020.eu
Social networks	Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter project accounts.
Press releases	3 formal announcements. First at M3
Project video	1 project video at M18
Flyer	1 flyer
Newsletters	4 newsletters. Two generic newsletters at the beginning and the end of the project, and two newsletters about pilots, after the initial phase and after the final deployment.
Local meetings	Number not specified
Technical Advisory Group	15 members maximum and 3 physical meetings
Exploitation Users Group	15 representatives maximum
Project events	2 large-scale project events
Workshops	8 technical workshops and 2 business workshops
Conference presentations	28 presentations (national + international conferences)
Conference posters	Number not specified
Demonstrations	Number not specified
Scientific Papers, Journal articles	13 scientific papers to indexed and peer-reviewed journals
Reports and other documents	Number not specified
Programme meetings	Number not specified

This table will record the commitments achieved during the project and will monitor their evolution

2.3 Project workshops

Workshop description	Resp.	Place	Date	Responsible
Workshop on INVADE concept and overall architecture model	UPC	Barcelona	M6	WP4
Workshop on INVADE architecture developed, focused on pilot implementation	UPC	Barcelona	M10	WP4
Workshop on grid integration of battery storages, with emphasis on benefits for distribution grid companies	VTT	Espoo	M14	WP6
Workshop on grid integration of energy storage, with emphasis on potential value creation.	NTNU	Trondheim	M17	WP5

Workshop on the second life of batteries, with emphasis on end of life criteria, safety, and refurbishing	VTT	Espoo	M21	WP6
Workshop on privacy and security, with emphasis on issues related to integration of EVs in the Internet of things	eSmart	Halden	M23	WP8
Workshop on INVADE architecture developed, focused on pilot implementation	NTNU	Trondheim	M28	WP5
Workshop on How Big Data Analytics and AI can contribute to increasing renewable energy integration	eSmart	Halden	M32	WP8

2.4 Events planning

External events	Q1Y2	Q2Y2	Q3Y2	Q4Y2	Q1Y3	Q2Y3	Q3Y3	Q4Y3
CIREN – International conference on electricity distribution								
IEEE-PES – IEEE PES general meeting								
IEEE-AMPS – IEEE International workshop on applied measurements for power systems								
EDSO – Events at European Distribution System Operators' Association for Smart Grids								
GEODE – Events at GEODE								
ETP Smart Grids – European Technology Platform for Electricity Networks of the Future general assembly								
EEE-ENERGYCON - IEEE International Energy Conference								
PSCC - Power Systems Computation Conference								
BEHAVE – Behaviour and Energy Efficiency conference								
ECEEE Summer study – ECEEE Summer study on energy efficiency								
IEEE-ISGT (Europe) – IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies								
EPE (Europe) – European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications								
PowerTech								
Solar Integration Workshop – International Workshop on Integration of Solar Power into Power Systems								
Energy Storage World Forum (Europe)								

3 Communication and dissemination guidelines

3.1 Communication timetable and content plan

An overall communication plan has been created (Excel file). The purpose is to ensure that the communication content is optimized and spread through the right digital channels to the right target group and to the right time.

It includes the following sheets: Communication timetable, detailed content plan, ideas bank, objectives and goals, social media strategy and accounts, milestones, meetings, deliverables, year-quarters and evaluation.

The purpose of the *timetable* is to provide an overview of the entire project period with planned activities, including milestones, deliverables and meetings. The timetable lists five phases (main objectives for communication based on the milestones) of the project, with planned content and ideas for each phase. In addition, it describes what channels (tools of communication) should be used, who the target audience is and what is the purpose of the communication. It also lists relevant participants and the person responsible for the communication in each phase. See the table of the *timetable* below:

Year	2017											
Month	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
Phases: Main objectives	Presenting the project						Expectations and trends					
Specific monthly goal?												
Milestones (See sheet)			MS1				MS2					
Deliverables (See sheet)			D2.1			D2.2 & D2.3						
Meetings (Additional workshops?)	3 meetings in Halden		Technical meeting in Barcelona and Stavanger	Online PCC-meeting		Workshop & TAG meeting in Barcelona	Online PCC-meeting			4 meetings in Barcelona		Program workshop in Brussels
Content (See sheet)	See detailed content plan and ideas bank						See detailed content plan and ideas bank					
Tool of communication	News articles on web site + social media						News articles on web site + social media					

Target audience	General public and stakeholders	General public and stakeholders
Purpose of communication	Informing the people about the project and explaining why it is relevant to them	Explaining what the expected impacts are and how the project can affect our world
Participants	All partners	All partners
Person responsible	Mette, Mari, Pol	Mette, Mari, Pol

The purpose of the *content plan* is to keep up timeliness and structure. The plan displays a timeline for the entire 3-year project period. The articles, news, posts and tweets will always be settled for a 2-month period in advance, allowing ad-hoc updates to compliment the plan. The content reflects the project's work tasks and the plan is created in accordance to the expected activities, events and happenings. It includes tool of communication, purpose, title/topic, interviewee, author/person responsible, image description, URL for web site, text for Facebook/Twitter/LinkedIn/Youtube. This is an internal tool to keep C&D actions updated. See the table of the content plan below:

Date	26-may	29-may	30-may	31-may	01-jun	02-jun
Status (draft, finished, published)	Published		Published	Published		Published
Tool/channel (news article, letter, social media post/tweet, scientific report)	Letter		Letter	Tweet		Tweet
Purpose (Inform, educate, engage)	Inform		Inform			
Title / Topic / WP	Stavanger workshop / WP9		St. Gallen / WP2	Stavanger workshop		Oslo project meeting
Contact / interviewee			Heidi Tuiskula			
Where to find additional information						
Author / Responsible partner and contact person for providing content	Mari Buckholm		Mari Buckholm			
Image description and location			6 images in word document from Heidi Tuiskula			
URL for web site article / blog post / publication	https://www.invadeh2020.eu/article2		https://www.invadeh2020.eu/article3			

Text for Facebook	NEW UPDATE: Because of the need to accelerate the INVADE business model work, a workshop was held in Stavanger in March. Read more: link		Smart Innovation Norway (SIN) participated in the 8th St. Gallen Forum for Management of Renewable Energies on May 11th and 12th, representing the two Horizon 2020 projects SIN coordinates, namely EMPOWER and INVADE. Read more: link (Del på NCE)			
Text for Twitter	In order to accelerate our INVADE #businessmodel work, a workshop was held in Stavanger in March. Read more: https://t.co/z1UGiem3O7		Smart Innovation Norway participated in the 8th #REMforum in Switzerland, representing the two @EU_H2020 projects @EmpowerH2020 and INVADE. Read more: link (Retweet by NCE)			
Text for LinkedIn						
Text for Youtube						

The purpose of the *ideas bank* is to schedule regular meetings for brainstorming ideas for each phase – and have somewhere to list them – before inserting the ideas where we see fit in the content plan.

The purpose of listing the *project objectives and communication goals* is to always have the project's overall objectives in mind when we plan our communication activities.

The purpose of listing the *social media strategy and accounts* is to be reminded of which accounts we manage and how to manage them.

The purpose of including the *milestones, meetings deliverables and year-quarters* in the communication plan is to easily find more information about where we are in the project – and plan the communication accordingly.

The purpose of the *evaluation* sheet is to have a way of documenting the effects of our communication work, including measurements (tools) and report frequency.

3.2 Journal and congress publications guidelines

Acknowledgment for all journal and congress publications is mandatory. The following sentence, or similar is recommended:

“This work has been supported by INVADE H2020 project, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 731148”

In any case, the project name and number, Horizon 2020 and European Union are compulsory and must be mentioned.

Without the acknowledgment the publication cannot be considered as a project activity.

According to the GA, all possible publications must be Open Access and Golden Access preferably. Green Access is the alternative of Golden Access in case it is not possible. For further information, check the information published in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual ([Link](#)) and the content developed by OpenAIRE H2020 project in their website ([link](#)).

All journal and congress publications of INVADE will be included in the [ZENODO](#) repository and they can be published in other repositories like [UPCommons](#) or others as well.

3.3 Social media guidelines

All partners are obliged to collaborate in social media activities like tweeting, posting activities on Facebook and LinkedIn, and others. All meetings between different partners should be published to maintain the interest of the target audience. Additionally, all partners should publish information like significant messages from our partners during meetings to explain our intentions, actions and operations.

The key objective is to outreach citizens as well as different stakeholder groups about the INVADE platform and its potential. The social networks will also be used to collect feedback and extract information from vital stakeholders, to utilize and improve the project's platform and its business and exploitation plan.

Four INVADE accounts have been created, with slightly different purposes:

Channel	Project account name	Project account link
Twitter	@invadeh2020	https://twitter.com/INVADEH2020
Facebook	Invade H2020 project	https://www.facebook.com/invadeh2020/
LinkedIn	INVADE H2020 project	https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/18070383
Youtube	INVADE H2020 project	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCMXP8Re01KixtAT4F8ZPtzA

Twitter will be used to cover ongoing news and updates from the consortium partners, and for collecting input and information. Twitter will enable the stakeholders to be involved directly with live discussions during a workshop or event. We have encouraged the consortium members to tweet about their everyday work with the project, and to tag/mention @INVADEH2020, which will always retweet. The content plan ensures a frequency of 3-5 tweets a week.

Facebook is to target the communication towards the younger generation, such as students, local media, and towards various national and local associations and communities promoting a sustainable way of living. Consequently, Facebook will require an appealing and rather sophisticated visual presentation of the project information because of the overload of information and advertisement in the feeds. Regular updates of 2-3 Facebook posts a week will be ensured by the content plan.

LinkedIn is considered a network targeting stakeholders of the European industry, initiatives and associations focusing on renewable energy storage, the smart grid, and novel ICT solutions for the energy sector. The channel will function as a trigger for different stakeholders (e.g. electric vehicles' owners). The overall LinkedIn activity will

follow the recommended update frequency described in the content plan, approximately 1-2 posts per week.

Youtube will be used to publish relevant videos. This communication channel will provide a more visual understanding of the project. Because we do not know when videos will be available, we will publish whenever something is created.

To sum up, the planned frequency of communicating through our social media accounts is as follows:

- Facebook posts: 2-3 times a week
- LinkedIn posts: 1-2 times a week
- Twitter updates: 3-5 tweets a week
- Youtube videos: Whenever something is made

The way to manage the social media accounts is described in the communication plan. The detailed content plan describes type/channel, purpose, title/topic, target audience, the choice of photo or film, when the post will be published and the responsible person for the publication. In addition to the planned articles/posts/tweets, we are always prepared for ad-hoc work and sharing/retweeting news relevant to the project.

3.4 Newsletters guidelines

Newsletters will provide updates about all important project milestones and achievements. See GA about project milestones.

All partners must contribute with updates for the newsletters.

3.5 Press releases guidelines

The consortium will strive to achieve broad coverage in selected national and international press and media throughout the project period. Consequently, activities and tasks in the communication and dissemination plan will be of great importance for influencing the press, as well as obtaining a good structure and guideline for the overall process of developing the content and distributing the press release through selected channels to desired medias worldwide.

3.5.1 Frequency, purpose and target audience

During the 3-year period, there will be created and distributed at least four formal announcements to national and international press and media, covering the start and end of the project and highlighting achievements of severe significance. The purpose is to inform, influence, engage and promote INVADE to selected stakeholders of the project. Thus, the press release should be of newsworthy character, whereas announcing important results, findings and outcomes that effects end users, society, businesses, politics and actors in the private sector.

3.5.2 Structure and content

The press release should be written as a formal and informative article, including the following elements:

- An introduction of INVADE (its purpose, objectives, expected results, etc)
- Concrete headline that describes the story in an appellative and credible way
- Description of the news, highlighting the main findings, results or achievements
- Statements from important and relevant persons involved in the news
- Images that describes the main heading of the story for the press to use
- Relevant logos: INVADE project and partners.
- Additional, detailed information about the project, findings, etc.
- Information about the partner in the project and contact persons for the specific press release.

3.5.3 Distribution and promotion

Spreading the press releases to international and national medias will be essential for achieving desired coverage and branding of the project. WP 2 team and INVADE project manager will be in charge of developing the press release and distributing it to the partners of the consortium. WP 2 leader will have the responsibility of supervising the contact with international presses and medias, whereas the partners will distribute the press release to their selected medias. A plan for distribution will be available, containing information about selected media / press, contact person, responsible partner for distribution and date / time for distribution.

The press release will be made visible and promoted through INVADE channels; website, social media platforms and newsletter. Additionally, each partner of the INVADE consortium will promote the press release in own website, social media accounts and newsletter by referring to press release on the INVADE webpage.

3.6 C&D activities repository

This document aims to collect all C&D activities during INVADE project from all partners. All partners have to report themselves their C&D activities in the excel file following instructions:

1. Fulfil at least mandatory fields according to Table 5
2. Keep it updated
3. Every partner is responsible to fulfil its own activities
4. Tweet with a picture about the activity and add the link (desired)

Table 5: C&D repository fields

Identifier	Automatic
English title	Mandatory
Type of activity	
Activity according to EC classification type	
Authors	
Date of publication	
Publisher	
Place of publication	
Open access type	
Partners involved	
Brief description	
Original title	
Link	
DOI	
ISBN	
Title of Journal/Proceedings /Book series	
Number, Date or frequency of the Journal / Proceedings Book	
Relevant pages	

4 EC events

Main goal for participating in EC events is the successful integration of INVADE into existing European projects landscape and fruitful contribution to events organised by the European Union bodies. Around 2% of the EU funding is dedicated for the coordination activities to be executed with similar EU-funded projects. Activities will be carried out in the task **T2.4 Participation in EC events and project clusters**, contributing to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between H2020 supported actions.

The project consortium will participate in **the EC programme workshops** organised by the European Commission and other European Union bodies to sum up and exchange the experiences and the output of the different projects. INVADE consortium will contribute to regulatory, research, policy formation sessions, and workshops or other events relevant to the European energy efficiency initiatives.

The project coordinator Mr. Dieter Hirdes (SmartIN) is a member of **Horizon 2020 Smart Grid and Storage projects' cluster [BRIDGE](#)** where a collaboration of now 31 EU funded projects is being reinforced through working group activities. Thus, the applicable outcomes of existing projects relevant to INVADE and results from projects that join the cluster in the future will be accessible for INVADE and will be exploited.

INVADE project has nominated the following BRIDGE representatives and our goal is to work actively in all four working groups.

Coordinator	Business Models	Customer Engagement	Data Management	Energy Regulation
Dieter Hirdes	Dagfinn Wåge / Gunnar Crawford	Trine Wildt Andersen	Erik Åsberg	Andreas Sumper

The coordinator of the project is also a member of the Horizon 2020 **Advisory Group of Energy (AGE) to the European Commission**. The Group is engaged in high level discussions on decarbonisation Scenarios of the EU 2050 Energy Roadmap, the SET-Plan and the Energy Union. The working groups' debates on Renewables, Smart EU Energy System with consumers at the centre, Sustainable Transport have a high importance to the integrated INVADE ecosystem.

5 Technical Advisory Group

5.1 TAG definition

The Technical Advisory Group (TAG) is an organization of experts about technical issues related to INVADE project that will collaborate providing their advice to the consortium. The TAG will collaborate providing feedback about technical specifications, functionalities and potential opportunities of the flexibility system.

The TAG has two levels of engagement:

1. Core members. Members that will follow up the project during the whole process and will attend all TAG meetings physically.
2. Satellite members. Members that will follow up the project during a certain period and will attend to some meetings physically.

5.2 TAG objectives

The main TAG objective is to provide guidance to the technical developments based on their experience. The profiles sought are the following:

1. Power system regulation
2. Energy retail business
3. Transmission system operation
4. Aggregation business
5. Internet of Energy
6. Privacy and security

TAG will physically meet at least three times

According to the GA:

“The TAG will not have any decision power, but will be consulted on relevant scientific and technical issues. The main purpose of the Group is to explore the key technological and policy priorities across the domain and implement them in core components of INVADE project. TAG members will be paid for their travel and accommodation expenses including daily allowances.”

“The purpose of this task is to allow the development of complementary and mutually supportive perspectives on the core components of INVADE project and to explore the key technological and policy priorities across the domain.”

“The Technical Advisory Group will be engaged in online discussions and will physically meet at least three times during the duration of the project, combined with the major events of the project organised within WP2 and WP3.”

6 Large scale events

In addition to all communication throughout the project lifetime there will also be held two large scale events during this period. Our goal is to target 100-150 participants at the actual events, further the content will be distributed on the website, to relevant press and medias and through all our Social Media channels in order to target a broader audience. These events are not single “one-offs”, but strategically placed as vital parts of the overall communication plan, including a follow-up plan to strengthen the effects of the events. The first event will be held in the middle of the project period at month 18 in Norway, and the second event will be held at month 36 in Spain. Smart Innovation Norway (SIN) will produce an overall plan for the event, including tasks such as event’s promotion and marketing, production of event material, agenda for execution, location, managing speakers and participants, economic and financial management, reporting and other tasks. The execution part will be divided between SIN in Norway, and UPC in Spain.

6.1.1 Target audience

The target audience for the two events will vary depending on the content, but it will mostly include DSOs, energy producers and smart-home service providers, as well as policy makers, representatives of public and private sector and end-users.

6.1.2 Content

The events will share some common content as to increase awareness of the project’s achievements and results, status and to interact and involve stakeholders. Thus, the two events will also differ due to the status of the project. The first event will mainly focus on the solution, progress and results and the second event will be more commercially driven.

Smart Innovation Norway will organize two different program committees that will work with the content for the two events. Planning and keeping track of these meetings is SINs responsibility.

6.1.3 Follow-up

To prevent these events from being just “one-offs”, Smart Innovation Norway will develop a plan in order to amplify awareness from the content produced from these events. The content will be a vital part of the overall communication plan and serve as branding

material for the second event, promotion of the overall INVADE project and as documentary of the projects progress.

7 References

- [1] B. A. Bremdal, "INVADE Stakeholders Engagement plan - D3.1," 2017.